

From Scoping Review to Practice: A Framework for Mapping Health Inequities in Rare Disease Diagnosis and Service Access onto the Health and Social Care Pathway

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Background

Health inequities are differences in health opportunities and outcomes which are avoidable, systemic and unfair.¹ We were commissioned by the United Kingdom (UK) National Institute for Health and Care Research (NIHR) Policy Research Programme to produce a scoping review of health inequities experienced by the rare disease community in the UK with respect to receipt of a diagnosis and access to health and social care services. This followed the commitment of the England Rare Disease Action Plan 2023 to work towards addressing inequities experienced by the rare disease community in these areas.² The resulting scoping review was conducted in adherence to established methodological guidance including patient and public involvement (PPI)³ and published in this journal.⁴ The review identified 136 relevant studies, including 96 UK primary studies and 40 international systematic reviews, within which seventeen types of health inequity experienced by the rare disease community were identified.⁴ Eleven of the identified inequities related to disparities between the rare disease community and the general population (see Table 1). The remaining six related to sub-groups within the rare disease community, which served to further stratify the eleven inequities experienced across the community as a whole. These sub-group characteristics were identified with reference to the PROGRESS+ health inequities framework and comprised place of residence, race/ethnicity, gender, socioeconomic status, age and disability.⁵

Table 1. Types of inequity experienced between the rare disease community and general population

Type of inequity	Description
Delayed diagnosis	Delays to receiving a diagnosis were experienced by PwRD.
Lack of knowledge	A lack of knowledge amongst clinicians could sometimes impact on receipt of a diagnosis of a rare disease and ability of PwRD to access appropriate services.
Lack of information	Clinicians would sometimes not provide or signpost to PwRD to sufficient information about a rare disease.
Limited services provision (comprising six types of inequity)	Challenges with accessing appropriate services, often related to limited services provision but also more specific challenges within different types of services. These included mental health services, emergency services, dentistry services, specialist services, social care services and services in general where these were not specified.

Limited services for undiagnosed conditions	Specific challenges amongst those with symptoms of a rare disease around accessing services when they do not have a diagnosis of a rare condition.
Lack of care co-ordination	Lack of care co-ordination between different health and social care services could adversely affect the receipt of a diagnosis and the ability to access accessing services after a diagnosis is received.

Abbreviations: PwRD=people with a rare disease

The scoping review narratively summarises the identified health inequities as they relate to receipt of a diagnosis and access to health and social care services, drawing out where these data are derived from UK-based studies.⁴ This establishes an understanding of the extent and nature of health inequities experienced by people with a rare disease (PwRD) in the UK. However, it does not show how the identified health inequities are structurally interrelated across the patient care pathway – for example, how inequities such as lack of knowledge or lack of information are experienced across primary, secondary and specialist services when seeking a diagnosis or accessing services, and how this affects outcomes such as delayed diagnosis. This relatively narrow focus reflects how scoping reviews aim to map the extent and nature of available evidence rather than interpret it in depth.³

An understanding of the structural interrelation of inequities experienced by the rare disease community—showing where and how PwRD experience health inequities across the patient care pathway, and the implications for diagnosis and service access—could be used to inform the development of targeted interventions aimed at addressing these inequities, thus further supporting the commitment of the England Rare Diseases Action Plan 2023.² To bridge the gap between the findings of the scoping review and the understanding required to inform practical action, we undertook further work to develop a framework of the structural interrelation of inequities experienced by PwRD across the patient care pathway. The framework was developed through further analysis of the data from the scoping review,⁴ with reference to Diderichsen and Hallqvist’s framework for describing pathways from social contexts to health outcomes.⁶ Specifically, the framework aims to support the identification of *contexts* along the patient care pathway that are associated with *mechanisms* leading to differential *outcomes*. In this respect, the framework also makes use of Pawson’s realist Context-Mechanism-Outcome heuristic as an interpretive lens, but does not comprise a full realist evaluation.⁷ Additionally, the framework highlights where evidence indicates that the identified mechanisms and outcomes are further exacerbated for sub-groups within the rare disease community.

In this paper, we present the framework we developed, including how it was developed and guidance on how to access and use it.

Framework development

Diderichsen and Hallqvist's framework aims to show how societies generate and maintain health inequities.⁶ Specifically, Diderichsen and Hallqvist's framework sets out an overarching context (society), within which there are mechanisms (causal explanations) which lead to differences in health outcomes for individuals and groups (health inequities).⁶ Furthermore, they intend that their framework is used to identify policy entry points for targeted interventions to address health inequities, by drawing attention to which mechanisms are producing which outcomes.⁶

For the purpose of our framework, we adapted the overarching societal context in Diderichsen and Hallqvist's framework to focus on *health policy, resourcing and organisation*, which reflects our aim to facilitate understanding of health inequities in the relatively narrower context of health and social care services delivery (see Figure 1).⁶ At the individual/group level (i.e. the overall impact that the mechanisms within the framework have on individuals and groups within society) we focused our framework on *social position and consequences of ill-health*; thus, we removed Diderichsen and Hallqvist's references to *specific exposure or disease/injury* at the individual/group level in our framework. We removed specific exposure because the majority of rare diseases are genetic, thus exposure is less relevant from the point of view of health inequity; and we removed disease or injury because, relatedly, we are solely interested in people who are already presenting with symptoms of disease, rather than where disease is a possible outcome relating to health inequity. Within this framework there are mechanisms which lead to disparities at the individual/group level.

Figure 1. Adaptations to Diderichsen and Hallqvist's framework

Within this revised framework, we structured the health and social care settings which the data for our scoping review showed that PwRD engage with into a patient care pathway, differentiating between receipt of a diagnosis and subsequent access to services.⁴ Some of these contexts were explicitly reported in the scoping review (see services listed under *Limited services provision* in Table 1).⁴ However, the process of identifying relevant contexts also involved re-visiting the raw data in

the data-extraction forms for data relating to the setting of health inequities which were not always reported in Briscoe et al., particularly where inequities which spanned several different contexts were not differentiated – for example, contexts relating to lack of knowledge and lack of information, which spanned primary, secondary and specialist services as well as social care.⁴ In some studies the specific contexts were not clear, thus we were not able to use all 96 UK primary studies included in the scoping review.⁴ We focused on data derived from UK-based studies, but also included international evidence from systematic reviews relating to one context where there was no UK evidence (maternity services).

Once we had mapped out the relevant health and social care contexts into a pathway, we linked each context to the various types of inequity identified in Briscoe et al. that PwRD experience within them.⁴ For the purpose of the framework, these were described in terms of mechanisms (e.g. lack of knowledge amongst clinicians, lack of information provision, or lack of care co-ordination) which lead to differences in outcomes (e.g. delayed diagnosis). We also sought to identify within the data where these mechanisms and outcomes are experienced differently for specific groups within the rare disease community, with reference to the PROGRESS+ framework.⁵ As with the identification of contexts, this process involved re-visiting the raw data in the data extraction forms. This sometimes involved additional interpretation of data which led to identifying new mechanisms and outcomes which were not described, or given distinct labels, in the scoping review. The full set of mechanisms and outcomes described in the framework are presented in Table 2, including those initially identified from Table 1.

Table 2. Revised set of types of inequity experienced by people with a rare disease, re-framed as mechanisms and outcomes

Type of inequity	Description
<i>Mechanisms</i>	
Accessibility	Accessibility issues included long wait times to access health and social care services and lack of availability of services.
Dismissive attitudes	Clinicians were sometimes dismissive of the symptoms of a rare disease, including with respect to the possibility of securing a diagnosis, and with respect to the impact of symptoms on daily living.
Lack of care co-ordination	Lack of care co-ordination between different health and social care services could adversely affect the receipt of a diagnosis and the ability to access services after a diagnosis is received.
Lack of information	Clinicians would sometimes not provide or signpost PwRD to sufficient information about a rare disease.
Lack of knowledge	A lack of knowledge amongst clinicians and social care staff could sometimes impact on receipt of a diagnosis (e.g. timeliness) and the ability for PwRD to access appropriate services.

Limited data sets	Limited data sets were identified as limitation for people seeking a diagnosis of a genetic rare disease, e.g. limited representation of ethnic minorities in data sets.
Wrong specialist	PwRD were sometimes referred to the wrong specialist for further tests, which impacted on the timeliness of diagnosis and the ability to access appropriate services.
<i>Outcomes</i>	
Delayed diagnosis	Delayed diagnosis was a commonly reported outcome of the inequities experienced when seeking a diagnosis and accessing services.
No- or mis-diagnosis	PwRD were sometimes given the wrong diagnosis or had their symptoms dismissed.
Not listened to	Not feeling listened to was reported by PwRD as a consequence of having their symptoms dismissed.
Patient satisfaction	Patient satisfaction was sometimes compromised due to the inequities experienced when seeking a diagnosis and accessing services.
Service avoidance	As a consequence of not receiving appropriate care when accessing services, PwRD reported avoiding health care services.
Variable care standards	Variable standards of care were experienced within the rare disease community in ways which are not just limited to the PROGRESS+ criteria. This included different standards of care experienced by people with different rare diseases.

Abbreviations: PwRD=people with a rare disease

The specific studies from Briscoe et al. from which data are derived for the mechanisms and outcomes described in Table 2 are presented in Table S1 and Table S2 in Supplementary Material 1.⁴ Data from 77 of 96 UK based primary studies in the scoping review are represented in the framework; in addition, there are data from two systematic reviews of international evidence relating to maternity services.

Importantly, the framework represents a dynamic interaction between the overarching context (health policy, resourcing and organisation), the health and social care contexts within the framework, and the social position and consequences of ill-health which are impacted by the mechanisms and outcomes represented. This is indicated by arrows which join the various contexts, and which move both backwards and forwards across the patient care pathway. We do not make recommendations in the framework for where interventions should be targeted to address the identified inequities, rather the framework is intended as a tool to facilitate this.

Presentation of framework

The framework is presented in a slide deck in Supplementary Material 2 in two stages: (1) receipt of a diagnosis and (2) access to services. The structure of the slide deck is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Structure of framework in the MS PowerPoint file

Slide(s)	Content	Notes
1	Title slide	Authors' institutional title slide with author list.
2	Instructions	Brief instructions on using the framework.
3	Patient pathway: receipt of a diagnosis	Depicts the contexts, mechanisms and outcomes associated with receipt of a diagnosis as a patient pathway, including detail about PROGRESS+ sub-group characteristics.
4	Patient pathway: access to services	Depicts the contexts, mechanisms and outcomes associated with accessing services as patient pathway, including detail about PROGRESS+ sub-group characteristics.
5-53	Elaboration on mechanisms and outcomes	Detailed descriptions of mechanisms and outcomes associated with the contexts depicted in the patient pathways on slides 3 and 4, including detail regarding PROGRESS+ characteristics of affected sub-groups. Slides 5-53 are accessed via hyperlinks in slides 3 and 4.

The framework is structured around a series of boxes which map onto health and social care services in the patient care pathway. The boxes representing service contexts are clear (i.e. not filled with colour) and labelled with the name of each service. Contexts relating to receipt of a diagnosis are presented in the first part of the framework (slide 3), and contexts representing access to services are presented in the second part of the framework (slide 4). *Health policy, resourcing and organisation* is represented as the overarching context in both parts of the framework. Mechanisms which lead to inequity within each context are presented in light shaded boxes, and outcomes arising from the mechanisms are presented in darker shaded boxes. Orange shading is used for the receipt of a diagnosis part of the framework, and blue shading is used for the access to services part of the framework. Each of the contexts, mechanisms and outcomes is assigned a number for ease of reference; however, the numbers do not necessarily indicate the order that someone moves through the pathway.

At the bottom of the framework is the exit point from the pathway (the individual/group level), which is labelled *social position and consequences of ill-health*. This feeds back into the service contexts.

Purple circular labels show which sub-groups are identified in the data as experiencing a particular type of mechanism or outcome. These labels correspond with the PROGRESS+ framework, including place of residence (P), race/ethnicity (R), gender (G), socioeconomic status (S), age (A) and disability (D).

Solid lines with arrows show links between different contexts, and dotted lines with arrows show links between mechanisms and outcomes.

Hyperlinks within each mechanism and outcome label are linked to text on slides 5-53 which provide a brief descriptive summary of mechanisms and outcomes respectively, and more detail relating to specific sub-groups affected. Each of slides 5-53 includes a hyperlink which takes the user back to the relevant pathway, i.e. diagnosis or service access. Further instructions on how to use the framework are presented on the second slide of the slide deck.

We are interested to receive feedback on this framework. Please email any feedback to s.briscoe@exeter.ac.uk.

References

1. McCartney G, Popham F, McMaster R, Cumbers A. Defining health and health inequalities. *Public Health*. 2019;172:22-30.
2. Department of Health and Social Care. England Rare Diseases Action Plan 2023: main report. Department of Health and Social Care; 2023. [Available from: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/england-rare-diseases-action-plan-2023/england-rare-diseases-action-plan-2023-main-report>].
3. Peters MD, Godfrey CM, Khalil H, et al. Guidance for conducting systematic scoping reviews. *Int J Evid Based Healthc*. 2015;13(3):141-6.
4. Briscoe S, Martin Pintado C, Sutcliffe K, et al. Evidence of inequities experienced by the rare disease community with respect to receipt of a diagnosis and access to services: a scoping review of UK and international evidence. *Orphanet J Rare Dis*. 2025;20(1):303.
5. Cochrane Methods Equity. PROGRESS-Plus 2023 [Available from: <https://methods.cochrane.org/equity/projects/evidence-equity/progress-plus>].
6. Diderichsen F, Evans T, Whitehead M. The Social Basis of Disparities in Health. 2001. In: *Challenging Inequities in Health: From Ethics to Action* [Internet]. Oxford University Press. Available from: <https://academic.oup.com/book/26479/chapter/194919341>.
7. Pawson R. *Evidence-Based Policy: A Realist Perspective*: SAGE Publications; 2006.